

Covalent immobilization of molecularly imprinted polymer nanoparticles on a gold surface using carbodiimide coupling for chemical sensing

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Versatile method for covalent immobilization of molecularly imprinted polymer nanoparticles on Au surface.
- Use of carbodiimide chemistry leads to covalently fixed uniform layer of organic nanoparticles with high density.
- Stepwise characterization of functionalized surfaces using microscopic and spectroscopic techniques.
- Optical sensing based on immobilized nanoparticles and surface enhanced Raman scattering.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

One challenging task in building (bio)chemical sensors is the efficient and stable immobilization of receptor on a suitable transducer. Herein, we report a method for covalent immobilization of molecularly imprinted core-shell nanoparticles for construction of robust chemical sensors. The imprinted nanoparticles with a core-shell structure have selective molecular binding sites in the core and multiple amino groups in the shell. The model Au transducer surface is first functionalized with a self-assembled monolayer of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid. The 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid is activated by treatment with carbodiimide/*N*-hydroxysuccinimide and then reacted with the core-shell nanoparticles to form amide bonds. We have characterized the process by studying the treated surfaces after each preparation step using atomic force microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, fluorescence microscopy, contact angle measurements and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The microscopy results show the successful immobilization of the imprinted nanoparticles on the surface. The photoelectron spectroscopy results further confirm the success of each functionalization step. Further, the amino groups on the MIP surface were activated by electrostatically adsorbing negatively charged Au colloids. The functionalized surface was shown to be active for surface enhanced Raman scattering detection of propranolol. The particle immobilization and surface enhanced Raman scattering approach described here has a general applicability for constructing chemical sensors in different formats.

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1. Introduction

Self-assembly of organic thiols on metal surfaces has been a very popular method to build up analytical systems for biosensing [1–3]. Different thiolates can be adsorbed on a variety of metal surfaces (Ag, Au, Cu, Pd, and Pt) [4,5]. In comparison to other metals, gold is the most common and popular for binding with alkanethiols due to its strong sulfur affinity [6]. Alkanethiols adsorbed on gold form a densely packed single molecule layer known as self-assembled monolayer (SAM) [7–10]. Due to their well-defined ordered arrangement, good electron transport, controllable electrical properties and availability of functional groups, SAMs have gained significant importance for immobilization of bio-recognition molecules.

SAMs containing terminal functional groups, e.g. carboxyl (–COOH) groups can be prepared on Au surface using 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA). The –COOH groups can be used to immobilize amino-containing molecules, e.g. proteins using the well-developed coupling reagents, 1-ethyl-3-(dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) [11]. The EDC/NHS coupling chemistry has been used for the development of different biosensors, biochips, and lab-on-a-chip using biological molecules as the receptors [12–15]. As the biological receptors are costly and have problems with stability (chemical and physical) and sensitivity in non-optimal environments, it is often necessary to switch to synthetic receptors with a high stability and cost effectiveness [16]. As an example, molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) with pre-designed recognition property have proven useful substitutes to biological receptors in practical applications [17,18].

One important aspect in the development of a MIP-based sensor is the appropriate interfacing of the polymer with the transducer. This can be made possible by either synthesizing the polymer *in situ* directly on the transducer surface or by coating the transducer surface with a pre-formed polymer. *In situ* synthesis of polymer directly on a surface can be achieved using electropolymerization or different surface-initiated, “grafting-from” radical polymerization [19–22]. A major problem associated with the *in situ* fabricated MIP sensors is, however, the inaccessibility of a large fraction of template sites due to the layers’ small surface area. This problem can be circumvented by immobilizing pre-formed polymer nano- or microparticles that possess a large surface-to-volume ratio. Reimhult et al. [23] and Kroger et al. [24] reported MIP particle attachment on a metal transducer surface using a polymer layer to construct a quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation (QCM-D) and electrochemical sensor, respectively. One potential problem using these approaches is that the thick interface polymer layer may cause additional non-specific analyte binding. In a previous work, Kolarov et al. reported an optical MIP sensor using a SAM of 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) to attach negatively charged MIP particles on surface [25]. However, electrostatic attachment does not offer sufficient particle fixation, particularly in the presence of electrolytes or in highly basic or acidic solutions that are commonly used to regenerate sensor surfaces. Therefore, it is necessary to develop suitable methods for covalent immobilization of MIP particles. Recently we reported a covalent approach to immobilize MIP core-shell particles using an epoxy silane SAM [26]. The method can be used to immobilize MIP particles on silica and other metal oxide surfaces. In this work we report another method that allows MIP particles to be covalently immobilized on gold, and demonstrate optical sensing of propranolol, a beta blocker drug used to treat high blood pressure, using surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS). A recent review on the coupling of gold nanoparticles with MIPs for the design of plasmonic-based sensors has been published by Ahmad et al.

[27]. Scheme 1 illustrates the approach used for immobilization of the MIP nanoparticles. In this approach, the clean Au surface is functionalized with MUA to form a carboxyl-terminated surface (step 1) followed by the EDC/NHS activation (step 2). In the final step (step 3) the surface is exposed to a solution of propranolol-imprinted core-shell MIP particles to finish the covalent amide bond. The short-chain alkyl thiol MUA created –COOH-functionalized SAMs that form a smooth and uniform underlying layer for the MIP attachment [28].

The EDC/NHS activation approach has various advantages such as high conversion efficiency, mild reaction conditions, easily separable byproducts and, most importantly, compatibility with the organic materials. These advantages of EDC/NHS activation of carboxylic acid followed by the amidation reaction make it ideal for covalent conjugation of MIPs on gold surface without affecting their binding properties. The surfaces are characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), fluorescence microscopy, water contact angle measurements and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Since the immobilization step affects only part of the amino groups on the MIP particles, it leaves the majority of the amino groups on the particle surfaces to be available for further functionalization. Here, the surface-exposed amino groups on the MIP core-shell particles were used to attach tannic acid/citrate-protected gold nanoparticles, thereby turning the MIP-coated surfaces into a suitable substrate for surface enhanced Raman sensing. Using these approach we are able to turn the immobilized MIP core-shell particles into SERS sensors for propranolol detection without complicated chemical reaction steps.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Acetone, acetic acid (glacial, 100%), acetonitrile (99.7%), azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN, 98%) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Methacrylic acid (MAA, 98.5%) was purchased from ACROS (Geel, Belgium). Propranolol hydrochloride (99%) supplied by Fluka (Dorset, UK) was converted into free base form before use. Allylamine (98%), *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) and *N,N*-methylene-bis-acrylamide (MBA) were purchased from Monomer-Polymer Laboratories (Windham, USA) and ICN Biomedicals Inc. (Warrendale, USA). Toluene, 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC, 98%), and *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, 98%) were from Sigma-Aldrich. Propranolol, L-[4-³H] (specific activity 20 curie/mmol, 50 μM) was from NEN Life Science Products (Boston, MA, USA). Before use, AIBN was re-crystallized from methanol. All other chemicals were used as received. Gold colloids (20 nm, protected by tannic acid/citrate and suspended in ethanol) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2. Methods

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) using a silicon cantilever tip from Veeco (meterology group, USA) was carried out in ambient environment using tapping mode to study the roughness and homogeneity of the prepared surfaces. The cantilever tip is *n*-doped silicon with a typical curvature radius of 10 nm, a force constant ≈10–130 N/m (PPP-NCHR-20), and a resonance frequency of 204–497 kHz. Evaluation of AFM images was performed using the Nanoscope software from Digital Instruments. The surfaces were further characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). To avoid charging the samples were coated with a 10 nm

Scheme 1. Steps involved for covalent immobilization of core-shell MIP nanoparticles on a gold surface.

Pt coating after preparation. The SEM was carried out on a SEM LEO 1560 microscope (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) with a loadlock and an 8" motorized stage, operated at 10 kV. Fluorescence microscopy was performed using a Nikon Eclipse E-400 microscope equipped with a CCD camera (Andor Technology, Belfast, Northern Ireland) with the purpose to detect the presence of MIP core-shell particles on carbodiimide activated surfaces. To label the MIP particles with fluorescent dye, the samples were dipped overnight into FITC (0.1 mg/mL) in acetonitrile solution. The MIP surfaces were then washed thoroughly in acetonitrile to remove the excess dye absorbed on the surface. The labelled surfaces were then examined under the fluorescent microscope with an excitation wavelength 495 nm and emission wavelength of 525 nm. Static contact angle measurements were done using a Contact Angle Module CA-1 from Sinterface Technologies (Berlin, Germany). A 5 μ L drop of Millipore water was dropped on the surface and the images were recorded after 5 s of the contact.

XPS was performed at the spectroscopy end station of beamline I311 on the MAX II electron storage ring of the MAX IV Laboratory in Lund, Sweden [29]. The instrument with separate preparation and analysis chambers (base pressures lower than 10^{-10} mbar) and a sample load lock is equipped with a Scienta SES 200 hemispherical electron energy analyzer. The samples were prepared *ex situ* and mounted on the sample holder using metal screws. This helped in creating a good electrical contact of the surface with ground and avoided any charging problem. The measurements were started after introduction of the sample and subsequent degassing once the pressure had recovered to 10^{-9} mbar. The X-ray photoelectron (XP) spectra were recorded with normal emission (i.e. 0° from the surface normal). All spectra were calibrated by the Au $4f_{7/2}$ peak of the sample at 84.0 eV binding energy, which is the Au $4f_{7/2}$ binding energy of bulk Au with respect to the Fermi level. A polynomial-type background was subtracted from all spectra.

Raman measurements were carried out using an iRaman system from B&W Tek Inc. equipped with an excitation laser at 785 nm and a source power of 325 mW. During the measurements the fiber optics probe was maintained at a distance of 6 mm from the sample surface. Raman spectra were collected in the range of $200\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a spectral resolution of 3 cm^{-1} . For each spectrum 5 scans were used, and each scan took 5 s. The spectra were recorded using the B&Wspec software and analyzed with Origin Pro 9.0. A background was subtracted from the spectra, which were then smoothed using the Savitzky–Golay method and normalized with respect to the Raman signal of the Au colloids at 1004 cm^{-1} .

2.3. Synthesis of MIP nanoparticles

Molecularly imprinted core-shell nanoparticles were synthesized in two steps according to the procedure reported by Hajiza-

deh et al. [30]. In the first step (*R,S*)-propranolol (137 mg, 0.53 mmol) was dissolved in 40 mL of acetonitrile in a (150×25 mm) borosilicate glass tube equipped with a screw cap. MAA (113 mg, 1.31 mmol), TRIM (648 mg, 2.02 mmol), and AIBN (28 mg) were then added to the solution. The solution was purged with a gentle flow of nitrogen for 5 min and then sealed. Polymerization was carried out in a Stovall HO-10 Hybridization Oven at 60°C (Greensboro, NC, USA), in which the sample was rotated at a speed of 20 rpm for 24 h. The polymerization step led to the formation of propranolol imprinted core particles. In the second step, NIPAM (566 mg, 5 mmol), MBA (77.2 mg, 0.5 mmol), allylamine (188 μ L, 2.5 mmol), and AIBN (24 mg) were added into the reaction tube and sonicated for 3 min. The mixture was then purged with nitrogen for 5 min before the mixture was allowed to polymerize for 48 h under a gentle rotation in the oven at 60°C . After the second polymerization the reaction mixture was centrifuged at 11,300g for 15 min to collect the polymer particles. The template was removed by washing the core-shell particles with methanol containing 10% acetic acid (v/v), until no template could be detected from the washing solvent by UV spectrometry using a wavelength of 290 nm. The polymer particles were finally washed with acetone and dried in a vacuum chamber. The non-imprinted polymer (NIP) core-shell particles were synthesized using the same protocol as described above, but without the template in the pre-polymerization mixture.

2.4. Preparation of Au-coated wafer

The Au-coated substrate was prepared by evaporating 200 nm Au onto a two-inch clean silicon (Si) wafer pre-coated with a 20 nm titanium adhesion layer. The Au-coated substrate was then cut into surfaces of $10 \times 10\text{ mm}^2$ size for further functionalization.

2.5. Preparation of self-assembled monolayer

To obtain high quality thiol-gold based SAMs, proper cleaning of the Au surface is necessary. Therefore, the gold surfaces were degreased by sonication in ethanol for 5 min and then placed in piranha solution ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, 7:3 v/v) for 30 min followed by washing in boiling water. The Au substrates were then dried under a nitrogen flow and immediately immersed in 1 mL ethanolic solution of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) (5 mM) for 24 h, followed by washing in copious amount of ethanol and then drying under nitrogen flow for further activation [31].

2.6. Immobilization of MIP nanoparticles

All the reagents and surfaces were prepared freshly and immediately before use. MUA surfaces were immersed in a 2 mL solution

mixture of 400 mM EDC and 100 mM NHS (1:1 v/v) in methanol for 2–3 h. The activated surfaces were washed in methanol and then immersed in a 1 mL MIP suspension in 1:1 (v/v) acetonitrile: water (2 mg/mL) with a constant horizontal shaking (140 rpm) for 12 h. Later the surfaces were rinsed in acetonitrile to remove all the physisorbed MIP particles followed by drying under nitrogen flow, and stored in vacuum until characterization.

2.7. Activation of MIP surface using Au colloids

To change the immobilized MIP surface into Raman-active substrate, we deposited 20 nm Au nanoparticles protected by tannic acid/citrate ligands on the MIP surface. Immobilization of the Au nanoparticles was done by drop casting 100 μ L of the commercial gold solution on the immobilized MIP and NIP surfaces. After the drop casting the surfaces were left to dry at ambient temperature for 12 h. The negatively charged Au nanoparticles were attracted to the positively charged polymer spheres via electrostatic bonding. The resulting surfaces were washed in water for 3–4 times to remove the loosely bound Au nanoparticles and then dried under nitrogen flow. The functionalized MIP and NIP surfaces were incubated in 1 mL propranolol solution (34×10^{-5} M) in acetonitrile for 3 h, rinsed with acetonitrile and then subjected to the SERS measurements.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 provides a short description of the surfaces prepared according to Scheme 1 along with their abbreviations, which then were characterized by different methods. The “Au”, “Au@MUA”, “Au@NHS” and “Au@MIP” preparations represent the steps of the scheme. In addition, we also studied control surfaces: the “Au + MIP” and “Au@MUA + MIP” preparation represents the non-

covalent or physisorbed MIP attached to clean Au and to a MUA SAM on gold.

3.1. Self-assembled monolayer of MUA

To achieve a dense and uniform MIP immobilization, a stable and uniform MUA layer is desired. Fig. 1 shows the change in contact angle for the water droplets when moving from Au (Fig. 1A) to a Au@MUA surface (Fig. 1B). The contact angle of $\sim 60^\circ$ for the Au surface decreases to 40° for the MUA surface, which is in line with what has been observed previously [32,33]. The contact angle measured on the Au surface was higher than that reported by Mrabet et al. [34], which might be caused by exposure of the surface to the atmosphere leading to some contamination. Nevertheless, the observation clearly indicates that the treatment with MUA introduces polar head groups ($-\text{COOH}$) on the Au surface and makes it more hydrophilic than the bare Au.

Table 1 provides the mean roughness (R_q) of the Au (2.1 nm) and Au@MUA (2 nm) surface calculated from the AFM images. The AFM images shows a smooth and homogenous Au surface before and after the SAM formation (Fig. 2A and C). The Au surface image is quite similar to what is observed using SEM (Fig. S1A). The inset of the image in Fig. S1A shows the densely packed gold particles obtained after Au evaporation on a silicon wafer.

XP spectra further confirm the chemical composition of the surfaces at each step. Overview scan of the Au surface before and after MUA functionalization show the increase in the peak intensity ratio of C 1s to Au 4f, confirming the formation of organic MUA layer on Au (Fig. S3B). Fig. 3A shows the C 1s spectra of the Au and Au@MUA surface. The peak at 284.5 eV is due to hydrocarbon impurities (C–C, C–H), as expected from *ex situ* prepared samples. For the Au@MUA surface, the main peak at 285.0 eV is assigned to the alkyl chain next to the carboxylic group [$\text{SH}-(\text{CH}_2)_{10}-\text{COOH}$]. The presence of an additional small shoulder at 286.0 eV and a peak at 289.0 eV are attributed to the carbon bonded to the sulfur [32] and the carboxylic groups of the Au@MUA surface [35]. The O 1s core level spectra of Au (Fig. 3B) show the presence of oxygen species as well. The piranha cleaning of the Au surface results in the formation of peroxide species (~ 531.6 eV) and $-\text{OH}$ from the water molecules (~ 533.0 eV), respectively [36]. The O 1s of Au@MUA surface consists of a main peak at 532.4 eV due to the C=O and a broad shoulder at ~ 533.5 eV due to the C–OH in the carboxyl group (cf. Scheme 1 (Step 1)) [37].

In the S 2p core level XP spectra of the Au@MUA surface, a doublet is observed due to the presence of S 2p_{3/2} and S 2p_{1/2} peaks. The binding energy of S 2p_{3/2} peak at 161.9 eV indicates the presence of sulfur atoms bound to the gold surface (Au–S). The presence of S 2p_{1/2} peak at ~ 163.2 eV indicates the presence of some unbound thiols [38]. However, an area ratio of 1:2 and a binding

Table 1
Short names of surface preparations and mean surface roughness (R_q) of the surfaces obtained using AFM.

Abbreviations of surfaces	Description of surfaces	Roughness, R_q (nm)
Au	Piranha cleaned gold	2.1
Au+MIP	Clean Au treated with MIP without covalent bonding	2.8
Au@MUA	Self-assembled MUA on Au	2
Au@MUA+MIP	MUA-modified Au exposed to MIP	65
Au@NHS	EDC and NHS-activated surface	2.4
Au@MIP	Covalently immobilized MIP on EDC and NHS activated surface	77

+, Without covalent bonding.

@, Covalent bonding.

Fig. 1. Water contact angle measured on the (A) Au, (B) Au@MUA, (C) Au@NHS, and (D) Au@MIP surfaces.

energy difference of ~ 1.2 eV between the S $2p_{3/2}$ and S $2p_{1/2}$ components of the S 2p line confirm the presence of the attached thiols (Fig. 3C). A broad peak at 168 eV indicates the presence of oxidized sulfur or sulfonates due to photooxidation of alkanethiols [39,40]. Low intensity S 2p XP peaks are also observed on the piranha-cleaned Au surface due to the sulfur attachment resulting from the sulfuric acid used during the piranha treatment. Fig. S3 shows the S 2p core level spectrum of the acetone-cleaned Au surface. The presence of a sharp peak at 168.0 eV confirms the presence of sulfonate species due to the *ex situ* contamination of the surface from the environment.

3.2. EDC/NHS activation

Compared to the Au@MUA surface the Au@NHS shows an increase in contact angle to 70° , which indicates the increase in hydrophobicity of the surface due to the formation of succinimide ester intermediate (*cf.* Fig. 1) [41]. Fig. 2E shows the smooth and uniform AFM morphology of the Au@NHS surface with an increased mean roughness (R_q) of 2.3 nm (*cf.* Table 1).

XPS results give more insight into the change in the SAM after activation. A strong evidence for the EDC/NHS activation is an appearance of the N 1s signal (Fig. 3D) and the increase in the C

Fig. 2. Tapping mode AFM topographical images and their respective sectional profiles for the different surfaces studied: (A) Au, (B) Au + MIP, (C) Au@MUA, (D) Au@MUA + MIP, (E) Au@NHS, and (F) Au@MIP.

1s to Au 4f peak intensity ratio (Fig. S3B). The first peak at lower binding energy of 400.0 eV indicates the presence of tertiary amine group [42] of EDC; the second peak at ~ 402.1 eV binding energy is attributed to photoemission from N–C=O (amide) due to the NHS ester group [43]. There is also a change observed in the C 1s core level XP spectra after the activation (Fig. 3A). The peak at 284.7 eV binding energy confirms the presence of carbon ring of NHS ester with some contribution from the alkyl part of the NHS molecules at 285.0 eV. The C 1s signals at 286.7 and 289.0 eV binding energy are attributed to photoemission from C–CON, and –COO of the NHS ester [44,45].

Three important peaks are observed in the O 1s spectra (Fig. 3B). The peak at 532.2, 533.6, and 534.5 eV binding energies are assigned to the C–O, N–C=O/C=O, and C–O–N components of the NHS ester [46]. Au@NHS surfaces still show the S 2p signal (Fig. 3C), characteristic of the organosulfur species chemisorbed on the gold surface.

3.3. MIP immobilization

Fig. S2 shows the fluorescence images obtained on the Au + MIP, and the Au@MIP surfaces. The FITC dye, with which the samples were treated before imaging, contains an isothiocyanate group reactive towards the amino group. No fluorescence is observed for the Au + MIP surface (Fig. S2A), indicating that all the MIP nanoparticles are lost during the washing. In contrary, a strong fluorescence signal is seen for the Au@MIP sample (Fig. S2B) due to the high density of the immobilized nanoparticles on the EDC/NHS-activated surface.

The water contact angle decreased from 70° to 20° between the Au@NHS and the Au@MIP surfaces, i.e. after MIP immobilization (Fig. 1). This implies that the surface becomes hydrophilic after

MIP immobilization, which is in line with our expectations: the MIP core-shell nanoparticles are hydrophilic due to the presence of abundant amino groups in the shell. Fig. 2A–F shows the AFM images of the Au, Au + MIP, Au@MUA, Au@MUA + MIP, Au@NHS, and Au@MIP surfaces, respectively, along with their respective sectional profile across the $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ area. From the AFM image of Au@MIP sample in Fig. 2F we observe a dense MIP coverage with an extremely rough sectional view (R_q of 77 nm, cf. Table 1) compared to the control surfaces, Au + MIP in Fig. 2B (R_q of 2.9 nm) and Au@MUA + MIP in Fig. 2D (R_q of 65 nm), indicating that the dense and stable MIP particles can be immobilized on the Au surface only after EDC/NHS activation. The reason for the physisorbed and inhomogeneous MIP attachment on the Au@MUA surface is due to the negatively charged –COOH groups that interacts electrostatically with the positively charged MIP particles. The AFM results are in agreement with the SEM images [Fig. S1(B–D)]. Hence, the NHS ester groups are required for activating the carboxyl groups of MUA and create a dense and covalent MIP assembly on the Au surface.

Fig. 3A and B shows the C 1s and N 1s XP spectra measured on the Au@MIP surface. The C 1s components are found at 284.8, 286.3, 287.0, and 289.0 eV binding energy, which we attribute to aliphatic (C–C/C–H), nitrogen-bonded (C–N), oxygen-bonded (C–O), and nitrogen- and oxygen-bonded (HN–C=O) species, respectively [47,48]. In the N 1s line we observe a strong peak at 401.3 eV binding energy due to the MIP particles which carry primary amine groups [49,50]. Possibly there is also a small component at 402.0 eV characteristic of remaining NHS ester, but from the overall line shape it is clear that most of the NHS intermediate has reacted [51]. The presence of these components is as expected for the XP spectra of the MIP particles. The O 1s spectrum (Fig. 3C) of the Au@MIP sample exhibit a broad distribution at higher bind-

Fig. 3. XP spectra obtained in normal emission geometry: (A) C 1s, (B) O 1s, and (C) S 2p of the clean Au, Au@MUA, Au@NHS, and Au@MIP surfaces, and (D) N 1s of the Au@NHS activated surface and the Au@MIP surface. Photoemission is from the underlined atoms.

Fig. 4. SEM images of (A) MIP surface with electrostatically immobilized 20 nm Au nanoparticles, and (B) NIP surface with electrostatically immobilized 20 nm Au nanoparticles.

Fig. 5. (A) Bottom to top: Raman signal detected from a MIP surface (Au@MIP), Au-activated MIP surface (Au@MIP@AuNPs), and Au-activated MIP surface after exposure to 3.4×10^{-4} M propranolol (Au@MIP@AuNPs@propranolol). (B) Bottom to top: Raman spectra collected from a NIP surface (Au@NIP), Au-activated NIP surface (Au@NIP@AuNPs), and Au-activated NIP surface after exposure to 3.4×10^{-4} M propranolol (Au@NIP@AuNPs@propranolol).

ing energy due to the presence of different oxygen bonded carbon and nitrogen species present in the MIP core-shell particles. The main peak at 534.0 eV attributes to the presence of N=C=O (amide) along with the broad distribution at higher binding energy at 534.5 eV (C—O—N) due to the NIPAM and MBA monomers of the MIP core-shell particles. The peaks at lower binding energy presents two contributions at 533.0 and 532.5 eV, which can be assigned to the —OH and C=O bonds [37] originating from the functional monomer (MAA) and cross-linker (TRIM). The high energy broadening of peak at 536–536.5 eV is due to water molecules [52] still left after MIP immobilization. Overall, we find clear evidence for MIP immobilization on the EDC/NHS activated surface (Au@MIP), which we attribute to a generation of NHS ester intermediate allowing the carboxyl to react with the primary amine on the MIP surface.

3.4. Activation of MIP surface for propranolol detection using SERS

To prove that the immobilized MIP particles maintain their selective molecular recognition for the original template, propranolol, we utilized the remaining surface amino groups on the immobilized MIP to attach 20 nm Au nanoparticles (AuNPs) to make the MIP surface to become Raman active. In this work the negatively charged Au colloids were fixed on the MIP surface via electrostatic interaction.

The high resolution SEM images in Fig. 4 show clearly the fixation of the 20 nm gold nanoparticles (bright dots) on the MIP (A)

and NIP (B) surfaces. The gold nanoparticles seem to be distributed uniformly on the MIP and NIP particles with a high surface coverage.

As shown in Fig. 5A, the activated MIP surface alone (Au@MIP@AuNPs), i.e. without any propranolol, shows no propranolol Raman signal. After exposure to a propranolol solution (3.4×10^{-4} M) the surface (Au@MIP@AuNPs@propranolol) generated a clearly visible Raman band at 1385 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5A), which can be attributed to the naphthalene moiety of the propranolol molecule [53]. In contrast, the non-activated MIP surface (Au@MIP) did not show any propranolol signal under the same condition. The reason for the enhancement of the Raman signal is due to the plasmonic coupling between the surface-bonded Au colloids combined with the enriched propranolol molecules through their specific binding to the MIP core-shell particles, resulting in effective local electromagnetic field enhancement [54,55]. For comparison, we also tested the response of the immobilized NIP nanoparticles to the same propranolol solution. As shown in Fig. 5B, after depositing Au colloids and exposure to the same propranolol solution, the NIP surface produced only a weak band at 1385 cm^{-1} that was difficult to distinguish from the base line. The sharp Raman band at 1004 cm^{-1} is caused by the phenol structure in the tannic acid ligands used to stabilize the Au colloids [56]. For the first time, we have demonstrated successful implementation of MIP nanoparticles for SERS-based chemical sensing through carbodiimide coupling. The result shows that the immobilized MIP particles maintain their selective molecular binding, which can be utilized

in the future for constructing MIP-based sensors using not only SERS, but also other signal transduction principles. Obviously, such MIP-based sensors are not limited to propranolol detection, but can be used to monitor other analytical targets as long as their high selectivity MIPs can be synthesized.

4. Conclusions

We have developed a new approach to construct MIP-based optical sensors for label-free detection using surface-enhanced Raman scattering. In this approach amino-functionalized MIP core-shell nanoparticles are first immobilized on carboxyl-functionalized gold substrate using carbodiimide coupling, the remaining amino groups on the MIP particles are then used to attach gold nanoparticles to turn the Au@MIP@AuNPs assembly into a Raman active surface with a pre-defined molecular selectivity. Using microscopic (SEM, AFM and fluorescence) analysis, water contact angle measurements and XPS analysis, we have verified successful surface modification after each reaction steps. The whole procedure for constructing the optical sensor is simple, reproducible, and efficient and does not require high temperature or special catalyst, which renders the method more robust and handy in comparison to other literature procedures. Given that different types of amino-functionalized MIP particles can be synthesized, our approach may be used to construct a large number of high selectivity SERS sensors for label-free detection of therapeutic drugs, environmental pollutants and biomarkers.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

SEM images, fluorescence microscopy, XPS overview scan and S 2p XP spectrum. Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2015.09.009>.

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